

An Internet of Things platform for heterogeneous data integration: Methodology and application examples

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Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized the industrial sector, yet digital transformation in this domain faces challenges due to the lack of standardized methodologies for IoT platform development. Many existing approaches struggle with issues such as data heterogeneity, lack of interoperability, and limited scalability when applied to large-scale industrial environments. In order to address the aforementioned gap, this work presents an IoT platform specifically designed for the agro-industrial sector, with interoperability as a core feature. Built using open technologies and an interoperable data model based on the OMA NGSI standard within the FIWARE framework, the platform enables seamless communication between heterogeneous devices and systems. Its scalable architecture allows the easy integration of new devices and scenarios. Additionally, the platform encapsulates industrial models (e.g., climate, production) as services and uses ETL processes to manage data heterogeneity, ensuring interoperability across systems. The platform, developed through a successful collaboration between academia and industry, has been validated in three sceneries that are exemplified in this work. To evaluate its scalability and performance, extensive load tests were conducted in a cloud environment, demonstrating its ability to handle high volumes of concurrent requests while maintaining efficient resource consumption.

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1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) has emerged as a revolutionary technology that has contributed to transform the industrial sector. Growing concerns about global challenges, such as climate change and the scarcity of essential resources, have placed IoT at the center of the global policy agenda [1, 2]. In response to these challenges, digital transformation has become an essential activity to improve production environments.

However, digital transformation on industrial domains has revealed challenges related to the lack of knowledge and standardization to develop IoT platforms. A recent study entitled "Why IoT Projects Fail" [3] highlights the need for greater knowledge in the design and architectures required for successful IoT projects. In such a context, simplified and effective methodologies and architectures are welcome.

In recent years, methods and frameworks for IoT applications development have been consolidated as a research topic [4, 5]. Complexity emerges when different techniques and technologies have to be integrated [6, 7]. These methods include frameworks for building IoT solutions in smart urban environments [8, 9], healthcare[10] and security monitoring [11], or production in industrial domains [12, 13].

In the literature, methodologies have been proposed to develop IoT platforms with remarkable features, such as interoperability [14, 15, 16], autonomy [17], smartness [18, 19], and scalability, which are critical to the success of IoT projects [19, 20].

However, to the best of our knowledge, the use of specific methodologies to develop IoT projects successfully is limited. Most existing methodologies focus, on the one hand, on the analysis and design stages, emphasizing stakeholder identification and characterization, as well as the elicitation of key requirements

and processes [21, 22, 15]. On the other hand, methodologies such as [19, 17] integrate simulation techniques to validate different IoT architectures before deployment. Other proposals focus on computing aspects while others adopt a hybrid network computing perspective [23, 24]. Furthermore, most of these methodologies have been developed for general-purpose applications, which limits their ability to address IoT-specific challenges, such as heterogeneity issues, interoperability, access to services, and scalability. Recent works like [25, 20] emphasize the need for standards and best practices to facilitate IoT integration, particularly for large-scale deployments.

The IoT platform described in this article is the result of considering, as critical requirements, the use of standardized data models to provide interoperability, and considering that both data and processes can be accessed through services. Therefore, this IoT platform has been designed to be interoperable from the beginning. Additionally, given that often industrial scenarios have underlying behavioral models (e.g., climate, growth, production, and so on), a proposal to encapsulate and expose these models as a service is also described. In addition, the IoT platform has been built following the methodology described in this article, which is characterized by a holistic approach, covering all stages of IoT project development, from conception to integration into real systems. Another feature is that it offers specific solutions to integrate pre-existing IoT platforms, such as FIWARE [26], and the development of large-scale decentralized IoT applications. A remarkable achievement of this approach is its proposal for the critical interoperability challenge, a recurrent issue in this context. In order to overcome this issue, the methodology uses a standardized data model and ETL services acting as a data gateway, collecting and dealing with heterogeneity issues, transforming data and adapting them to the standardized data model. Finally, this methodology is result of a successful partnership between academia and industry, making it useful and applicable in a variety of situations.

While existing methodologies have made significant strides in addressing key challenges in IoT system development, they often fall short in providing a

unified and scalable approach tailored for industrial applications. Many frameworks emphasize conceptual modeling, simulation, or architecture definition, yet lack practical implementations that can be seamlessly integrated into large-scale IoT ecosystems. Additionally, the heterogeneity of IoT devices and data formats remains a fundamental challenge, limiting interoperability and hindering real-world adoption. Unlike these methodologies, our proposal not only defines a robust architecture but also provides a practical implementation that integrates heterogeneous data sources while ensuring interoperability through a standardized approach. By leveraging open technologies and the OMA NGSI data model under FIWARE, our platform enables efficient communication between diverse IoT systems. Furthermore, scalability is addressed through a cloud-based deployment model, capable of dynamically allocating resources based on demand, ensuring high availability and resilience in large-scale deployments. These aspects distinguish our approach from existing solutions and demonstrate its suitability for real-world industrial applications.

Therefore, the main contributions of this work are as follows:

- An IoT platform paired with a methodology to integrate heterogeneous data in agro-industrial sectors is proposed. The proposal is based on open technologies and it is supported by a standard and interoperable data model under the OMA NSGI [27] standard of FIWARE. So, the complete data production cycle from the lower layers to the upper layers of services is enabled.
- A reference architecture for data and service integration is described, from the bottom device layer to top application layer.
- The use of the architecture and methodology to build real agro-industrial scenarios is exemplified, providing a successful application of the methodology and the architecture to current and real-world scenarios.
- Finally, real scalability tests of the proposed platform are presented, demonstrating its ability to dynamically adjust resources based on demand and

maintain stable performance under high-concurrency conditions.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the background to data integration, FIWARE, interoperability, data heterogeneity, scalability, and explores related work. In Section 3, components required for the development of an IoT platform, the reference architecture, and the used methodology are detailed. Section 4 outlines the facilities used for the development and the integration of the methodology with real successful use cases. In Section 5, the scalability tests of the platform are presented. Section 6 presents the results and discussion. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the conclusions.

2. Background and related work

This section provides a broad overview of essential and underlying concepts of our approach to service integration in the context of the IoT. It is focused on the relevance of data integration [28], interoperability [29] and scalability [30], which can be considered fundamental issues in the development of an IoT platform [31]. Underlying technologies, as FIWARE [26] and Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPC UA) [32] are also introduced. In addition, a review of existing relevant papers published in this field is carried out, depicting their relevance and significant contributions in the area of interest. This literature review serves as reference to highlight the contribution of this paper.

2.1. Background

2.1.1. OPC UA

Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPC UA) is presented as the evolution of traditional OPC. OPC is the standard in the automation, monitoring, and process control sectors in the industrial sector. OPC UA was created in 2003 as a service-oriented architecture that allows communication regardless of manufacturers and platforms. It focuses on client-server communication and operates over TCP/IP. As a unified architecture, it provides

a complete level of interoperability from device to semantic data model for data exchange between platforms and enterprises [32]. OPC UA is cross-platform and suitable for use in multi-domain scenarios and on the Internet [33].

2.1.2. FIWARE

The European Union is advocating for the adoption of IoT platforms to enhance efficiency and sustainability. In this context, FIWARE [26] is a freely available framework established as part of a European initiative that involves collaboration between the public and private sectors to shape the future Internet. FIWARE operates on a modular structure, underpinned by a range of Generic Enablers (GEs) providing functionalities and standards to make the development of smart applications easier. By allowing integration with third-party components, FIWARE enables rapid deployment of smart solutions. GEs simplify the interaction with IoT systems, contextual data, API management, and information processing and analysis. Next, a list of main GEs is outlined:

- **Orion Context Broker (OCB):** An essential and mandatory component in any FIWARE-based solution. This component handles system context information using a decentralized and scalable approach. A remarkable issue is related to it does not retain historical data. This task is performed by other enablers (e.g. Cygnus, STH Comet).
- **Cygnus:** This component deals with storing historic data.
- **STH Comet:** This component stores historic data in short periods of time, usually in months.
- **IoT Agents:** These elements play a significant role transforming contextual information to the FIWARE NGSI standard [34]. IoT Agents are placed between the information generation layer and the OCB. IoT Agents support various formats, protocols and standards, including LWM2M over CoaP, JSON or UltraLight over HTTP/MQTT, and OPC UA [32]. Besides, a customized agent may be created, enabling adaptation to specific user requirements.

- **Cosmos:** It allows processing large data volumes providing integrations with current Big data platforms like Apache Hadoop [35], Apache Spark [36], and Google Cloud BigQuery [37].
- **Wilma:** It acts as a security layer offering proxy functionality based on OAuth2 schemes.
- **Perseus:** It allows to generate a series of alarms, making subscriptions to the OCB entities notifying changes using SMS, Email, or HTTP notifications.

2.1.3. Interoperability

Given the definition provided in [28] as “the ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and use the information that has been exchanged”, the use of common standards to make communication between IoT devices easier must be considered.

In the IoT context, interoperability is achieved through the development and adoption of standards that enable systems to communicate and share services with each other [38]. This connectivity capability is crucial in an environment where device and data heterogeneity is continually increasing.

However, interoperability leads to a significant challenge in order to develop a successful implementation in an IoT project. Devices that have to work together efficiently meets data and interface heterogeneity. The plenty of APIs, data models, formats and else used by manufacturers becomes a headache for developers when trying to adapt applications to handle vendor differences and achieve the desired compatibility.

To address these challenges, in our proposal, the use of open and common standards that encourages interoperability in the IoT ecosystem is promoted. Adopting standards-oriented approaches, a better compatibility between devices and systems may be ensured, making easier integration, innovation, and developing flexible and scalable IoT solutions.

2.1.4. Data heterogeneity

Data heterogeneity leads to another challenge due to the diversity in the structure, format, and type of data generated by connected devices [28]. In IoT systems, a wide spectrum of data sources is present, such as sensors, actuators, and other devices, each with its own communication protocol and data format. This diversity makes integration, processing, and analysis harder.

Despite of data interoperability is crucial to ensure that different IoT systems and devices may communicate, share data, and collaborate effectively, data heterogeneity may keep interoperability off when data uses different structures, communication protocols, or is constrained to privacy and security restrictions.

In this context, platforms such as FIWARE and data models, such as OMA NGSI (Next Generation Service Interfaces) [34], have emerged as candidate solutions to address data heterogeneity in IoT environments. FIWARE provides a set of open standards and technologies to facilitate interoperability and data integration in IoT applications. On the other hand, the OMA NGSI data model offers a common approach for modelling and exchanging data in IoT environments, enabling greater consistency and compatibility between different systems and devices.

Our proposal is based on the adoption of open standards and interoperable technologies, such as FIWARE and OMA NGSI, to address data heterogeneity in IoT environments. By promoting data harmonization and interoperability between platforms, we aim to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of IoT solutions, empowering data generated by connected devices.

2.1.5. Scalability

In IoT context, scalability means the system ability to handle an increase in the number of connected devices, the volume of generated data, and the associated workload, without a performance or service quality degradation [30]. A lack of scalability can limit IoT system ability to meet changing market demands, expand into new markets, or support emerging applications and services.

Our solution addresses the challenge of scalability in IoT systems by imple-

menting scalable and efficient architectures and technologies. Adopting design approaches that provide scalability, IoT systems may grow and evolve flexibly to meet the changing needs of users and processes. In particular, the use of a microservice architecture providing REST API services to the data layer allows scaling the platform horizontally to incorporate new devices or new industrial scenarios. Even, the use of a microservice architecture with interchangeable components ease to jump to new technologies and emerging trends in the IoT field.

2.2. Related work

The search for an IoT solution for heterogeneous data integration is an interesting research topic in the scientific community.

Some authors propose extending or enriching a software engineering methodology for IoT. [21] highlights that a full-fledged IoT methodology is missing providing a deep study of existing proposals. A methodology is proposed to support the main engineering phases of IoT systems and applications placing emphasis on requirements elicitation at system and *things* levels. The methodology provides metamodels for smart objects at different abstraction levels, and it is applied to develop a Smart University Campus scenario using a multiagent approach.

[23] is focused on IoT architecture. It provides guidelines for designing multiagent systems using the Prometheus methodology. Traditional software development lifecycle, from the requirements specification to a detailed design, are covered by the methodology, basing the approach on objectives and goals.

Other methodologies are based on simulation. [19] uses agents to drive software development towards the *things* within IoT systems. These agents are characterized as software entities operating independently. The methodology consists of three steps: a modeling step to generate a system specification in terms of agents; a simulation step of simulations including performance indicators to be tested over functional and non-functional requirements; and, an implementation step to code the requirements established on the first step and

fulfilling the indicators defined on the second step. In [17], a framework for creating robust, collaborative IoT systems at the edge is introduced, leveraging spatial proximity, opportunistic agents, and coordinating nodes. This engineering strategy is both declarative and adaptable, dynamically segmenting the environment into collaborative zones managed by edge devices. An implementation is described as a collective, self-organizing workflow rooted in Aggregate Computing, with evaluation conducted through simulation.

The lack of standards for IoT as well as methodologies to fully support the development of heterogeneous, interoperable and integrated IoT systems is emphasized in [22]. Authors present a methodology to support the integration process of heterogeneous IoT platforms from the analysis to the maintenance phase.

A review of methodologies, frameworks, platforms and tools used in the context of developing IoT systems is described in [25]. The review is used in terms of interoperability, autonomy, smartness and scalability. Those concepts are also defined to reduce confusion, ambiguity and misuse of these terms. Authors highlight semantic annotation to make interoperability easier, as well as the use of Model-Driven Design (MDD), service oriented architectures, microservices, and smart agents. The value of autoconfiguration for security management, access control and authorization is also addressed. Besides, the use of open and public REST APIs to provide syntactic interoperability is emphasised.

Other authors propose a methodology for IoT application development that divides the process into distinct aspects and offers a conceptual framework for application development [15]. A development framework to implement the proposed methodology is also described. The framework provides automation strategies across various stages of IoT application development to reduce the development effort uses techniques for code generation and task mapping. A MDD approach is also used to make IoT application development easier. Another work that uses MDD to propose a methodology for IoT applications is described in [39]. The goodness of generating models at different abstraction levels (object layer, network layer, service layer and application layer), the gen-

eration of software components, as well as the decomposition of complex systems into loosely coupled components is described. A four layer architecture based on SOA is proposed. The methodology is applied to a scenario for smart vehicles.

In [40], the Smart Environment Metamodel (SEM) framework is introduced. It is designed to model applications within the smart environment domain. SEM employs both functional and data perspectives to guide analysis, design, and implementation. The framework includes a functional metamodel focusing on system functionalities and interactions, and a data metamodel describing properties and relationships of data sources. Basic guidelines are also described to show how the framework may be used.

Authors of [20] describe the use of a methodology to make easier the design, setup, and management of IoT projects through the provision of project templates, checklists, and architecture solutions. Nevertheless, it does not focus on details about software development and testing processes. The methodology consists of two steps. First, it outlines the strategy and the business. In the next step, an initial design and process workflows are proposed. A repository of reusable project artifacts is used as basis for the current project.

Another methodology is proposed in [14]. Authors describe it as an agile, interactive, technology-independent and incremental methodology. It divides the process on three steps. First step deals with understanding the business as well as the problems to be addressed in terms of objectives and expected benefits, description of the proposed solution and stakeholders. Second step defines the functional and non-functional requirements. Third step is focused on implementation, evaluating the technology and choose the best options. Monitoring how information is delivered to users is also carried out in this last step.

In [18], a multi-agent IoT system architecture is defined delineating both similarities and distinctions in the platform. This architecture serves as a foundational model, establishing a shared platform and customizable elements for each autonomous software component (agent). Agents are used as a convenient solution due to their distributed nature.

In [41], Stack4Things (S4T) is presented as an OpenStack-based framework

designed for orchestrating IoT and computational resources in a distributed environment. S4T introduces mechanisms for dynamic resource allocation, device federation, and efficient data processing at the edge, enhancing the scalability and resilience of IoT deployments.

Finally, [42] proposes a software product line development process for IoT agents, and [43] proposes a model-based approach to software engineering in IoT.

Based on the above literature review, a detailed comparison of the related works in terms of interoperability, scalability and evaluation methods, and our proposal is provided in Table 1. As can be observed, our proposal is based on the use of a standard model following an architecture and a methodology that allows interoperability between devices and other IoT platforms. Scalability and a successful application in real environments are also features of our proposal.

Table 1: Comparison between IoT Development Methodologies.

Paper/Methodology	Objective	Interoperability	Scalability	Method of Evaluation
[21] ACOSO-Meth	Design and implementation of IoT systems	Not specified	Yes	Theoretical
[28] Prometheus-based methodology	Develop a multi-agent system for IoT systems	Not specified	Not specified	Theoretical
[19] EIDAMeth	Rapid prototyping based on visual programming	Yes	Yes	Simulation
[17] Engineering of robust collaborative IoT systems at the edge	Develop components for the network edge	Limited	Yes	Simulation
[22] INTER-METH	Integration of heterogeneous IoT platforms	Yes	Yes	Theoretical
[25] Review of methodologies, frameworks, platforms, and tools	Review of methodologies, frameworks, platforms, and tools	Yes	Yes	Theoretical
[15] Methodology for IoT application development	Methodology for IoT application development	Yes	Yes	Theoretical
[39] Methodology for IoT application development based on MDD	Methodology for IoT application development based on MDD	Yes	Yes	Theoretical
[40] Smart Environment Metamodel (SEM) framework	Model applications within the smart environment domain	Yes	Yes	Theoretical
[20] Methodology to facilitate design, setup, and management of IoT projects	Facilitate design, setup, and management of IoT projects	Yes	Limited	Theoretical
[14] Agile, interactive, technology-independent, and incremental methodology	Develop IoT projects in an agile, interactive, and incremental manner	Yes	Yes	Theoretical
[18] Multi-agent IoT system architecture	Define architecture for multi-agent IoT systems	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
[42] Software product line development process for IoT agents	Develop software product lines for IoT agents	Yes	Yes	Theoretical
[43] Model-based approach to software engineering in IoT	Model-based approach to software engineering in IoT	No	Yes	Theoretical
[41] A Stack4Things-based Web of Things Architecture	Management and orchestration of heterogeneous IoT devices	Yes	Yes	Practical
Our proposal	Integration of heterogeneous data in real agro-industrial scenarios	Yes (NGSI FIWARE)	Yes	Tested in a real environment

Furthermore, while several IoT platforms exist, such as Google Cloud IoT, AWS IoT Core, and FIWARE Orion Context Broker, the proposed platform is characterized by its modular architecture and adaptability to heterogeneous data sources. Unlike cloud-centric solutions, which heavily rely on vendor-specific services, our framework offers an open and customizable alternative, adapted to environments with limited resources. Moreover, the integration with FIWARE enhances data interoperability and contextualized decision-making in various domains. A comparative analysis of real-world implementations further underscores the strengths of our approach in terms of interoperability, data

management, and scalability.

3. An IoT platform for agro-industrial domains

The methodology proposed in this work introduces an IoT platform offering an end-to-end solution specifically tailored to address the challenges of integrating heterogeneous data in agro-industrial domains. The following sections provide a detailed description of the key components, the proposed reference architecture, and the implementation workflow.

3.1. Key IoT platform components

Basic components used to develop the IoT platform and its requirements are shown below.

- **IoT devices:** These are the generators of context information. These devices, such as sensors and IoT stations, gather real-time data on working conditions of the different domains and other relevant parameters associated with production. Robust sensors and actuators designed to work in these conditions must be used; otherwise, issues related to reliability, measurement errors or out-of-range sensors will emerge.
- **Connectivity:** Robust connectivity infrastructures are required to allow efficient communication of devices with the core platform. Communication protocols, such as industrial Ethernet, and radio frequency technologies such as GPRS, MQTT, and LoRa are typically used to ensure reliable data transmission, even in rural environments with limited connectivity.
- **Heterogeneous Data Integration:** One of the most critical aspects of the platform is its ability to address the diversity of data in the agro-industrial domain. A flexible data model to support a wide range of data formats and information sources must be used. In this case, an approach based on the OMA NGSI standard of the FIWARE platform has been

implemented, acting as the semantic core for data integration. So, interoperability between different devices and information systems gets easier, overcoming one of the biggest challenges in the IoT, providing horizontal and not only vertical interoperability.

- **Data Processing:** Advanced data processing capabilities are implemented in the cloud. This includes the use of data processing techniques to clean, transform, and enrich data. Data processing is a fundamental pillar for the development of customized algorithms that serve as a decision support system.
- **Data Storage:** All data collected must be sent to a scalable and secure data storage system. A storage approach based on data distribution and replication solution is used to provide a centralized repository with high availability for storing data at large scale.
- **Cloud services:** Making data and application services available is essential in the current business model of IoT systems. IoT services should be available as cloud services to be accessible from any REST client or web system in order to be integrated with others.
- **Security:** Given the sensitivity of the data collected and the growing concern about cyber threats, special attention has been paid to security at all levels of the platform. Robust security measures are implemented to protect data, communication, and the integrity of IoT systems in general.

3.2. Conceptual architecture

This subsection introduces the conceptual architecture used in the development of the proposed IoT platform and its corresponding methodology. The architecture, illustrated in Figure 1, has been designed to enable integrating heterogeneous data. On the one hand, it provides generic services, as data access services. On the other hand, specific services to model or mimic domain tasks or processes are also available. This example includes a Greenhouse Model

as a Service (GMaaS) [44], which provide domain models (e.g. temperature, humidity, cultivation growth, and so on) as another cloud service through a REST API.

A remarkable achievement of this approach is its proposal for the critical interoperability challenge, a recurrent issue in this context. In order to overcome this issue, the methodology uses a standardized data model and ETL services acting as a data gateway, collecting and dealing with heterogeneity issues, transforming data and adapting them to the standardized data model.

Core architecture is based on a three-layer and two cross-layer conceptual architecture: perception, data storage/processing, application, security and management. This layered structure allows the development of customized services and enables the integration of new scenarios, as well as expanding existing ones (e.g, adding new devices). Architecture layers are described below:

Figure 1: Design of the proposed conceptual architecture

1. **Perception layer:** It is located at the bottom of Figure 1. It is the sensory layer of the IoT platform where objects identify their environment, gather data from the physical world, and interact with it. The context information needed for the standard data model is generated in this layer.

This term refers to all data generated by sensors/actuators in the environment belonging to the IoT ecosystem. This layer is composed of all types of sensors and actuators that transform information into electrical signals that are easier to transmit for further analysis. Figure shows the four industrial sectors used during the development of this IoT platform, such as greenhouses, an industrial photobioreactor plant, a water desalination plant, and an smart building. It should be noted that this layer allows adding new devices, as well as adding new industrial scenarios horizontally. In other words, the system is designed to be scalable, allowing new greenhouses, photobioreactors, desalination plants and buildings to be added, along with their respective sensors and actuators.

- **Sensors, actuators, and Smart sensors:** In our platform, there are different types of sensors and actuators, such as sensors connected to SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) systems or PLCs (Programmable Logic Controllers) through a wired network, sensors connected to IoT stations, or smart devices that send information to a manufacturer REST API or to the architecture upper layer autonomously. Industrial sectors need robust sensors. So, traditional sensors connected by cable to LabJack acquisition cards or industrial PLCs are integrated in this layer. Besides, IoT stations or smart sensors record data over longer periods of time. For instance, the data retrieval interval might be in minutes, whereas the data is typically transmitted to higher layers every 1 hour or 24-hour intervals. Different kind of sensors are available for temperature, radiation, CO₂ levels, pressure, soil moisture, wind speed, light intensity, and more, depending on the target industry sector. Each sensor and IoT station operates with distinct sampling frequencies, so a subsequent processing to standardize the data is needed.

2. **Data storage and processing layer:** It is located at the center of the conceptual architecture (see Figure 1). It provides services related to data

extraction, processing, and loading from sensors of the perception layer, databases, and a set of FIWARE GEs (including translators from various communication protocols, such as MQTT and OPC UA, to the OMA NSGI standard). Data models are also proposed for the interoperability and storage of historical time-series data. In addition, processing services are offered to assist decision-making processes based on domain models offered as cloud services (e.g. GMaaS).

- **ETL:** The process known as Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) is used in data integration to get data from multiple sources, transform it to meet user requirements, and load it into a data lake or another data storage system. In our proposal, the ETL process is in charge of retrieving data from REST services or other formats that are not directly linked to the FIWARE platform. ETL tools are available to transform data to the NSGI standard.
- **Orion Context Broker (OCB):** At the core of our architecture lies OCB, which manages the data generated by sensors in the Perception Layer. OCB uses the OMA NSGI standard [27], which comprises entities, attributes, and metadata. OCB manages sensor and actuator attributes, including data types, values, and metadata. It is important to highlight that entities and attributes can be generated in different ways through OCB, ETL processes, or IoT Agent. A distinctive feature of OCB is that it does not store historical data, but only retains the latest sensor state. Therefore, when a new value is sent, the previous value is overwritten. If historical data storage is required, another GE must be used, such as Cygnus or the development of a specific REST API for such a functionality. OCB allows subscriptions to a REST API service. Notifications are sent to subscribers when values are modified. The subscription address must be provided to OCB. After modifying a subscribed attribute, data is automatically sent to a Cygnus endpoint. OCB provides dif-

ferent types of subscriptions for each entity, allowing a mapping of all data and enabling adding new sensors into the system. To store entities and their values, a MongoDB database is used attending its scalability features.

- **NGSI data model:** The OMA NGSI data model provides a flexible and powerful structure for representing entities, attributes, and their metadata in an IoT environment. The proposed platform uses the NGSI data model to represent entities that correspond to industrial plants (see Table 2). Each entity in the NGSI model represents a unique instance of an IoT environment, allowing data management and analysis on any scenario. Entities in the NGSI model are defined by a set of attributes that describe their properties and characteristics. These attributes can include information such as the geographical location of the plant, associated sensors and actuators, production process data, inventory levels and any other information relevant to the operation and management of the plant. By using the NGSI data model, data may be structured in a consistent way, which makes interoperability between different systems and applications easier. In addition, model flexibility allows us to adapt to changing requirements and add new attributes or entities as needed.
- **IDAS NGSI Agent:** It is a FIWARE Enabler component used to streamline the connection of devices and systems to the OCB through the NGSI standard. This agent gathers data from IoT devices and sends it to the OCB for further analysis. Benefits of using these agents include the ability to link with IoT devices, standardize and enrich data, making development of smart applications easier, and achieve scalability and flexibility through its modular design. Moreover, a key feature is its support for two-way communication between the OCB and sensors connected to IoT agents, such as OPC UA and MQTT, like in the proposed platform.

Table 2: Data model

Key	Value
EntityId	Entity identification
EntityType	Description of entity type
AttributeName	Sensor name
AttributeType	Sensor type
AttributeValue	Sensor value
MetadataName	Metadata name
MetadataType	Metadata type
MetadataValue	Metadata value

- **Cygnus:** It is the last FIWARE Enabler used in the platform. Cygnus was designed to manage data persistence in external storage systems, such as databases, file systems or big data systems. It acts as a middleware between OCB and storage systems, making the integration of real-time data generated by IoT devices and other systems easier. The advantages of using Cygnus are the adaptability to different storage systems simultaneously, data transformation and enrichment, and the scalability and performance to manage a large data volume. In our proposal it is used to persist data.
- **GMaaS:** An interesting feature to be included in the proposed IoT platform is GMaaS. GMaaS exposes a model encapsulated as a cloud service. Current available models are greenhouse climate models, tomato growth model and irrigation models. Underlying models are implemented in *MATLAB Production Server* [45]. Model processing is carried out in this layer. Details about this proposal can be found in [44].
- **Database:** Depending on the operational and domain needs, different databases may be used to store data from each industrial sector. Both relational and non-relational databases are allowed.

In the case of MongoDB, data is generated by OCB notifications through data delivery to a REST API for custom data storage, and another using the Cygnus enabler for storing raw information. The use of non-relational databases, such as MongoDB, enables to have a data model based on OMA NGSI, enabling interoperability. MongoDB offers a flexible data model that allows the storage of unstructured data, making adding sensors and actuators with different attributes easier because no schema has to be modified. Additionally, MongoDB allows for horizontal scaling through sharding and replication techniques, distributing and replicating data across different nodes in the MongoDB cluster. This horizontal scaling capability is essential for efficiently handling large volumes of data in constantly growing IoT systems.

In the context of relational databases, the proposed architecture allows the use of applications requiring a more rigid structure and complex relationships between data. Data may be generated by Cygnus or by ETL processes performing aggregation and triage operations. Relational databases are used when data integrity and consistency in complex transactions are required, such as the use of SCADA systems for local plant monitoring or control algorithms. Figure 1 illustrates the use of a Postgres database for customized applications for plant technicians, such as dashboards or SCADA systems. Dashboards have been built with Grafana [46].

3. **Application layer:** Located at the top of Figure 1, this layer exposes applications, interfaces, and services to end users. Users or businesses services use these components to interact with the services and sensors in the lower layers. This layer provides features such as real-time sensor data information, register new sensors, store current and historical data, get weather forecasts, use GMaaS models, and so on. These features are also available as a REST API [47]. In addition, a graphical interface is

also available. Interaction between GUI and the system is carried out by means of REST API services. These end user applications and services allow users to monitor and manage data in the cloud. Some of these services are described below:

- **Provisioning services:** Services offered to generate context information, allowing adding new sensors, actuators and industrial sectors.
 - **Data services:** Services to query historical data aggregated or unaggregated. Query results can be downloaded in different formats such as JSON or CSV.
 - **GMaaS services:** A set of domain models has been developed and encapsulated as cloud services. These models are accessible through a specific REST API. They can be used for different purposes: as a simulation tool, where model inputs can be obtained from historical data or from a weather forecasting service; as a real-time virtual sensor for control/feedback purposes, where the model is invoked just one step ahead; and as a graphical DSS service from a web-based application.
4. **Security layer:** The security of the proposed IoT platform leverages OAuth2 for authentication and authorization, ensuring secure access control across services. Additionally, for device authentication, X.509 certificates and JWT-based mechanisms are employed to prevent unauthorized access. JSON Web Token (JWT) tokens can be used by IoT devices at the perception layer to prevent data from being sent by other types of agent and to control users at the application layer with different roles and permissions. Besides, our platform incorporates end-to-end encryption using TLS and DTLS.
 5. **Management layer:** In the management layer, a role and permission control system is implemented to regulate access to system resources and functionalities. Roles can be assigned to individual users or groups of

users, and each role has specific permissions associated with it, such as the use of GMaaS that determine what actions a user can perform in the system. In this management layer, the devices of the perception layer and the maintenance of the database and related services of the data storage and processing layer are also registered.

3.2.1. Service Discovery and Composition for Efficient Orchestration

Efficient service orchestration is essential for IoT platforms, enabling seamless interaction between heterogeneous services while optimizing resource consumption. To achieve this, our platform implements a dynamic service discovery and composition mechanism, ensuring interoperability and scalability in industrial environments.

Service discovery is managed through a centralized service registry using the OCB of FIWARE, which maintains an up-to-date catalog of available services. Services register via the NGSI standard, exposing their metadata, interfaces, and availability in a structured format. Clients can retrieve services dynamically through context queries, binding to resources based on real-time conditions. Additionally, an event-driven notification system allows components to subscribe to changes in service availability, ensuring continuous adaptation to evolving network conditions.

For service composition, the platform follows a loosely coupled microservices architecture, allowing modular integration of various functionalities. Services communicate asynchronously using message queues such as MQTT or HTTP callbacks, enabling reliable data exchange without direct dependencies. A dynamic ETL pipeline ensures seamless data transformation, standardizing information into NGSI-compliant formats. Furthermore, industrial models, including climate prediction and irrigation control, are encapsulated as GMaaS, allowing seamless integration of advanced analytics.

Service orchestration follows a hybrid approach, combining decentralized execution with intelligent resource allocation. Services operate independently while receiving context updates from OCB, ensuring real-time coordination. To

enhance performance, the platform incorporates load balancing and distributed processing, preventing bottlenecks by dynamically allocating tasks across multiple nodes. Additionally, the system leverages historical and real-time sensor data to optimize energy consumption and response times, ensuring efficient service execution under varying workloads.

By combining dynamic discovery, event-driven composition, and decentralized orchestration, our platform enables scalable, resilient, and adaptive service management. These capabilities ensure that industrial IoT applications can efficiently integrate heterogeneous services while maintaining performance and reliability in large-scale deployments.

3.3. IoT architecture implementation for industrial sectors

This section provides an overview of the steps and processes required to a successfully implementation of proposed IoT architecture in industrial sectors, following the flow chart presented in Figure 2. The description of each step is presented below:

1. **Definition of Objectives and Scope:** Define the scope of the project: Which are the industry sectors are involved in this implementation? What types of sensors and actuators will be used in the project? This will provide an overview of the dimensions of the project. Besides, identify the specific objectives of the implementation of the IoT architecture in the selected industrial sector. This includes establishing what the implementation is expected to achieve, such as improving operational efficiency or optimizing resource consumption.
2. **Industrial Sector Requirements Assessment:** Perform a detailed analysis of the specific requirements (functional and non-functional) of the selected industry sector. This includes understanding the operations, critical data, regulations, and control needs of the industry in question. Gather information about specific characteristics of the industry sector that can affect the implementation of the IoT architecture.

Figure 2: IoT Architecture Implementation Methodology for Industrial Sectors

3. **Sensor and Actuator Selection:** Based on previous requirements assessment step, select the adequate sensors and actuators. It is essential install robust sensors and actuators designed to work under these conditions. Otherwise, issues related to measurement errors or out-of-range sensors will arise. Consider the connectivity of these devices and their interoperability features, especially in relation to the OMA NGSI standard, OPC UA and REST API services.
4. **IoT Architecture Design:** Using the information collected in the previous steps, create a detailed design of the IoT architecture. This includes defining how the three layers (perception, data storage/processing, and application) are structured. Define the network topology to be used and the communication interfaces between layers. This ensures that data flows efficiently within the system. This three-tier architecture design makes it easy to use for a research center as it can focus on functionality.

5. **Data Model and Standards:** In this phase, a data model based on recognized standards, such as OMA NGSI, is established to ensure data interoperability throughout the architecture. In addition, communication protocols and standards that will be used to ensure data compatibility between the different components of the architecture are defined.
6. **Implementation of the Perception Layer:** The development of the Perception Layer is a crucial part of the implementation. This layer includes sensors, actuators, data acquisition cards, and SCADA systems. Sensors and actuators must be configured to enable real-time monitoring and effective data collection. In addition, robust communication must be established between these devices.
7. **Implementation of the Data Storage and Processing Layer:** This layer deals with storing and processing data which be used later in the Perception and Application layers. It contains all the key components such as databases, Orion Context Broker, Cygnus, ETL and Data Filtering processes. Each of these elements must be configured to effectively manage the data generated by all the devices.
8. **Implementation of the Application Layer:** In this stage, we proceed to develop all the services to be exposed to users, which includes key components such as applications, REST API services, Models as services, and so on. Each of these elements must be configured and put into operation to manage effectively the data generated by the sensors and actuators by retrieving information from the Data Storage and Processing layer.
9. **Testing and Validation:** Once the Perception and Data storage and processing layers have been implemented, extensive testing is essential in a controlled environment. These tests must validate the correct operation of all components, communication between devices, data interoperability, and the integrity of the system as a whole.
10. **Pilot Implementation:** After a successful testing, pilot implementation is carried out in a real environment of the selected industrial sector. This phase allows the developer to evaluate the performance and efficiency of

the architecture under real operating conditions. The results of the pilot implementation will be fundamental for making final adjustments and improvements.

11. **Optimization and Scalability:** Once the pilot implementation is complete, it is essential to identify areas for architecture improvement and optimization. This may include tuning performance, efficiency, and responsiveness of the system. In addition, the scalability of the architecture to add new sensors, actuators, or industry sectors is evaluated in the future. Optimization and scalability are ongoing processes to keep the system performing best.
12. **Documentation and Training:** Documentation plays a critical role in the effective management and operation of the IoT architecture. Comprehensive documentation should be developed, including detailed user manuals, implementation guides for the Perception Layer and the Data Storage and Processing Layer, and REST API documentation to access and interact with external services. Additionally, a training process is provided to both users and personnel involved in the operation and maintenance of the system. This training is essential to ensure that the system is used effectively and securely.
13. **Continuous Monitoring and Maintenance:** Once the IoT architecture is working, a continuous monitoring system is established to monitor the performance and integrity of the system at both layers. This involves constant monitoring of the Perception Layer and the Data Storage and Processing Layer to detect potential problems, failures, or performance degradations. A preventive and corrective maintenance plan is implemented to address any issues that arise and ensure uninterrupted system operation.

Beyond its application in the agro-industrial sector, the proposed IoT platform has been designed to offer adaptability to other IoT domains. The use of standardized communication protocols, such as OMA NGSI, MQTT, and OPC

UA, facilitates interoperability across different sectors, including manufacturing, logistics, and smart cities. The OMA NGSI data model provides a flexible and structured approach to representing entities and attributes, enabling integration between systems and applications. Additionally, the platform employs IoT Agents to convert MQTT messages into the NGSI standard, which can facilitate its incorporation into various environments. Previous studies have explored the implementation of FIWARE-based architectures in smart cities. For example, the Gaia-X and FIWARE initiative [48] has developed federated data platforms to integrate heterogeneous data sources in smart cities, promoting secure and standardized data exchange. Similarly, the GreenMov project [49] has applied NGSI-LD and FIWARE in urban mobility, integrating environmental data (air quality, traffic, noise) to optimize real-time transportation recommendations. In this context, structuring our platform around these principles could support its expansion beyond agriculture, providing a viable alternative for broader industrial applications.

3.3.1. Agents and roles

Each development methodology needs to have well defined agents and roles [14]. This definition is important for the organization and structuring of the solutions. Our proposal has the following agents playing the following roles:

- **Client:** Includes all stakeholders that will be served by the system.
- **Project Manager:** Acts as a liaison between the Client and the Development Manager. Responsible for extracting information from the business and verifying the feasibility of the solution together with the other stakeholders. All communication between the Client and the Development Manager is handled through the Project Manager.
- **Development Manager:** Responsible for managing the multidisciplinary team. Defines the parameters related to the development of the solution. This role also defines the responsibilities in each phase of the system and

oversees the development of the project. Organizes the requirements gathering, acts as a bridge between the multidisciplinary team and the Project Manager. It may also be in contact with the Client.

- **Multidisciplinary Development Team:** Formed by professionals with experience in the different levels of the system, it is responsible for the development process.

4. Application examples

This subsection describes the scenarios that motivated the development of the IoT data integration platform described in this article and that has served as application domains. In order to show the usefulness of the IoT platform, a set of greenhouses, a microalgae biorefinery and a small-scale agro-industrial environment have been used as an experimental basis (see Figure 3). The heterogeneity of this working environment has been selected to illustrate the scalability of the proposed IoT solution and the adaptability of the used methodology on different industrial scenarios.

Figure 3: Representation of the agro-industrial district

4.1. Agricultural domain

This IoT platform has been developed in two phases. Initially, a pilot greenhouse located at the Cajamar Foundation Experimental Station in El Ejido, Almería, Spain, was used (see Figure 3). This greenhouse emulated the conditions of commercial tomato greenhouses. Advanced sensors and actuators were installed on it. There were installed sensors for a wide range of climatic and crop parameters, such as temperature, humidity, solar radiation, CO₂, and so on, getting values every 30 seconds. In addition, there were actuators to control heaters, illumination, CO₂ enrichment systems, and so on. Data acquisition was performed using National Instruments data acquisition systems connected to an SCADA system. This facility served as the initial testing and development environment for the IoT platform.

In the second phase, the scalability of the IoT platform was evaluated. It was scaled from the described pilot greenhouse to eight real greenhouses in production, distributed in three different geographical areas of the province of Almería, Spain. These greenhouses have surface areas ranging from 7,400 to 30,000 m². Each of these greenhouses includes data acquisition stations of different brands, such as Hortisys, iMetos and HOPU, which provide measures for a wide range of agricultural and climatic parameters (see Figure 3). Data is sent to ETL and acquisition services using GPRS or Wi-Fi. This phase was used to test the scalability of the IoT platform on environments with production greenhouses using different greenhouse types, as well as scaling the amount of devices and introducing device heterogeneity. Additional information on sending and managing data on the developed IoT platform can be found in [31].

4.1.1. Case study development

In this section, the steps of the methodology described on section 3.3 are outlined to illustrate how can be applied to develop a scenario in agricultural domain. Each step is followed by a description as well as considerations about the application in the scenario.

1. **Definition of Objectives and Scope:** Before starting the development of the case study, specific objectives and the project scope were defined. Main objective included the implementation of an IoT platform for monitoring and implementing control algorithms as a service for greenhouses. Platform scalability and crop efficiency were also objectives. The project scope is delimited to the selection of eight production greenhouses located in different geographical areas of the province of Almería, Spain.
2. **Industrial Sector Requirements Assessment:** A detailed analysis of the specific requirements (functional and non-functional) of the selected agricultural sector was conducted. This included understanding the daily operations within agricultural farms, which vary depending on the crop, used agricultural practices, and the specific environmental conditions of each region. In terms of functional requirements, main operations and critical processes for efficient management of an agricultural farm were identified. Activities such as monitoring environmental conditions, irrigation and fertilization management, pest and disease control, monitoring crop growth and development, and harvest and post-harvest planning were identified. Additionally, non-functional requirements related to performance, scalability, security, and system interoperability were evaluated. Handle a large data volume generated by multiple IoT devices distributed across different geographical locations, as well as ensuring data integrity and confidentiality were identified. Interoperability with existing and future agricultural systems was also considered, using open standards and communication protocols used in the industry, such as OMA NSG1.
3. **Sensor and Actuator Selection:** Sensors and actuators were selected based on the evaluation of agricultural sector requirements. Robust devices designed to work in adverse agricultural conditions were used. Advanced sensors and actuators were selected and deployed in greenhouses to measure a wide range of climatic and crop parameters, such as temperature, humidity, solar radiation, among others.
4. **IoT Architecture Design:** Using the information gathered in the previ-

ous steps, a specific IoT architecture for monitoring and controlling agricultural greenhouses was designed, paying attention to system scalability and interoperability (see Figure 4). Services and data storage must be designed to grow elastically. Architecture is designed to be service oriented. The three layers (perception, data storage/processing, and application) were defined, and communication interfaces between them were established. Details are described in section 4.1.2.

5. **Data Model and Standards:** In this stage, a data model based on OMA NSGI was implemented to standardize the representation and exchange of data between components of the IoT architecture. Each entity of the OMA NSGI data model is an IoT station, a sensor, or a set of sensors (see table 3).
6. **Implementation of Perception Layer:** The development of the Perception Layer (see section 4.1.2) includes set up sensors, actuators, and data acquisition systems to enable real-time monitoring and effective data gathering. Weather stations and data acquisition systems were implemented and configured in greenhouses to acquire real-time climate and crop data.
7. **Implementation of Data Storage and Processing Layer:** In this stage, the Data Storage and Processing Layer (see section 4.1.2) was implemented. It deals with storing and processing gathered data for later use in the Perception and Application layers. Key components, such as the IoT Agent, OCB, Cygnus, database clusters, ETL processes, data filtering, and GMaaS processing core were configured and deployed to effectively manage data generated by devices in greenhouses. Processes at this level are encapsulated as microservices and are deployed to be scalable.
8. **Implementation of Application Layer:** In this stage, services and applications of the Application Layer (see section 4.1.2) exposed to end-users are developed. REST API services and web applications, such as iVeg, were developed to provide end-users access to stored data, analysis and models as a service functionalities, providing decision-making support

(see section 4.1.3).

9. **Testing and Validation:** After implementing previous steps, tests were conducted in a controlled environment to validate the correct operation of the system at application layer, as well as to ensure its integrity and interoperability. Tests were carried out to validate the collected data, device communication, data interoperability, deployed services and system integrity.
10. **Pilot Implementation:** Once the tests have successfully passed, the pilot implementation of the system in a real environment of selected production greenhouses was carried out. This phase allowed evaluating the performance and efficiency of the system in real operational conditions. The IoT system was implemented in eight production greenhouses distributed in different geographical areas, allowing the evaluation of scalability and effectiveness in real agricultural production environments.
11. **Optimization and Scalability:** After completing the pilot implementation, improvement issues were identified, and tuning tasks were made to optimize system performance and efficiency. Additionally, system scalability to add new devices and industrial sectors was evaluated. Adjustments and optimizations were made in the IoT system to improve its performance and scalability. Additional IoT stations were incorporated adding new devices and agricultural sectors to the platform.
12. **Documentation and Training:** Documentation resources for an effective system management and operation were developed, including user manuals, implementation and operation guides, and API documentation. Additionally, training sessions were defined for end users, as well as for users involved in system operation and management tasks.
13. **Continuous Monitoring and Maintenance:** Once the IoT system was running, a continuous monitoring system was established to monitor system performance and integrity across all layers. A preventive and corrective maintenance plan was implemented to address any issues that arose and ensure uninterrupted system operation. This included monitoring net-

work traffic, server resource utilization, database integrity, performance of application services, and availability of IoT devices. Alert thresholds were also defined over platform metrics.

4.1.2. Architecture

This subsection describes the specific architecture used for the development of the IoT platform. As mentioned in section 3.2, this always starts from the conceptual idea of such an architecture needed for the development of a heterogeneous data integration platform in IoT. The functionality of each of the elements that make up the architecture is described below:

Figure 4: Architecture and services in the agricultural sector

1. **Perception Layer:** In our case study, eight greenhouses with tomato crops located at different geographical in Almería, Spain, have been used. These greenhouses include various meteorological stations that consist of sensors such as those for CO₂ levels, solar and overall radiation, air and soil moisture, electrical conductivity, water usage, air and soil temperature, among others. The specific sensors present in a station are determined by its model and the manufacturer. Additionally, the greenhouses

may incorporate supplementary sensors and actuators that are connected to storage and processing systems. Figure 4 illustrates the relationships between greenhouse devices and data workflows to the upper layer. Meteorological stations, data acquisition systems, and SCADA computers share their data using RESTful services. Nevertheless, the data provided exhibit heterogeneity as they do not adhere to any standardized formats.

2. **Storage and Data Processing Layer:** This layer is in charge of processing and extracting data from the perception layer. It has different elements such as:

- **IoT Agent, ETL and polling processes:** This service focuses on retrieving contextual information, transformation and sending to the IoT platform. It consists of two components: the IoT Agent and the polling processes. The IoT Agent converts sensor readings to the FIWARE NGSI standard to solve the heterogeneity problem between sensors. The service is configured to get sensor data from various sources, including REST services, IoT devices, and smart sensors. In this case, it focuses on HOPU (currently called Libelium IoT) station integration. This station allows data to be sent to a MQTT broker. This IoT Agent allows to subscribe to the topic of this broker and to transform data to the data model established for its operation in Orion Context Broker (OCB). The other component is polling process (e.g Linux Cron) that periodically retrieves data from IoT station REST APIs, external weather systems and SCADA systems. Polling processes query and extract data from sources and carry out a transformation to the established NGSI data model. Finally, transformed data is sent to OCB.
- **OCB:** It is a FIWARE component that deals with providing real-time data from sensors and actuators. Data is standardized by the data model defined before (see Table 2), which allows the interoperability of the information. In addition, it allows data producers

and consumers to establish a common data model. Different types of entities are available, each of them associated to a set of sensors, either IoT stations or SCADA systems (Table 3). In order to get a unique reference to the different types of stations in the same entity, FIWARE-Service and FIWARE-ServicePath are used, providing hierarchical scopes. The first element defines the name of the greenhouse, while the second element defines the name of the IoT station or set of sensors. Each of the sensors is defined with its name and value in the attributes. Metadata is available within these attributes, giving the possibility to create fields such as date when reading the data, common name, and so on.

Table 3: Entities used in the OCB for greenhouses.

EntityId	EntityType	AttributesName	AttributesType	AttributesValue	MetadataName	MetadataType	MetadataValue
Hopu191	Station	relativeHumidity,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.1,2024-03-04T21:00:00
Meter191	Station	relativeHumidity,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.2,2024-03-04T21:00:00
SCADA191	SCADA	relativeHumidity,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.3,2024-03-04T21:00:00
iMetos191	Station	relativeHumidity,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.4,2024-03-04T21:00:00

- **REST API:** The proposed architecture provides two different services (see Fig. 4): a service for data persistence and a service for managing incoming requests. Both services are encapsulated within the RESTful API module. On the one hand, service run subscriptions for each available entity. As previously outlined, the use of OCB enables entities to subscribe. After updating any attribute of a subscribed entity, a notification is broadcasted to all services subscribed to that entity. Next, an HTTP request is dispatched to the persistence service, which verifies the existence of data and timestamp within the system before storing the measurement. On the other hand, another service provides a REST API that can be used by end users. End users send requests to endpoints described in Table 4. Response data is returned in JSON format. This service can be used either by means of a REST client or using the developed web application, iVeg.

- **GMaaS:** This component deals with GMaaS processing, exposing models as a service. It is based on MATLAB Production Server. The component uses parameterized physical models to interact with greenhouses devices. It provides a REST API that gets required parameters and methods to perform control operations. After processing requests, results are returned to the client in JSON format. This new approach of models as a service was proposed in [44].
 - **Database:** Data is stored in different non-relational databases. A database is used by OCB for real-time data storage. Another database is used by the REST API services to store historical data. A flexible data model is used, so that unstructured data can be stored. Therefore, sensors and actuators of IoT stations with different attributes can be added without modifying the stored data. Furthermore, MongoDB, a non-relational database, provides horizontal scaling using sharding and replication techniques, distributing and replicating data through cluster nodes.
3. **Application Layer:** This layer exposes data to end users through iVeg Data Service and iVeg Graphics web interfaces. iVeg has been deployed in the context of the IoF2020 project, which focuses on digitalizing agriculture [31]. Initially, iVeg integrated various data sources from various service providers, capturing data from sensors and actuators over different time frames. Therefore, greenhouse sensor and actuator data may be stored on the platform databases by means of a REST API. Data from various devices is stored with a flexible sampling interval ranging from 1 to 20 minutes, depending on the nature of the data to be preserved. Stored data is used for fine-tuning and feed models for indoor climate, crop yield, and irrigation within the platform, which can be accessed as REST API services.

4.1.3. Proposed services

This section describes the services available for sensor and actuator registration, industry sectors, historical data querying and GMaaS services. Table 4 provides a summary of available services and endpoints.

Table 4: Data Services

Service	Method	Endpoint
Provision IoT Devices	POST	/iot/devices/
Query IoT Devices	GET	/iot/devices/
Register IoT Entity	POST	/v2/entities/
Query IoT Entity	GET	/v2/entities/
Historical Data	GET	/api/getDataSensorGreenhouseAnalyticsFechasV3
Historical Last Data	GET	/api/getDataSensorGreenhouseLastDataV4
Weather forecasts	GET	/forecast/hourly?
Climate model	POST	/api/modelsclimatotal
Production model	POST	/api/modelsproduccion
Irrigation model	POST	/api/modelsriego

- Provision IoT Devices:** This service allows adding new devices, such as sensors, actuators or greenhouses into the system. It belongs to the FIWARE provisioning group and translates the HUPO IoT station (currently called Libelium IoT) data into the OMA NGSI standard of OCB. Initially, the devices must be registered with the service. Once the sensors are registered, the IoT agent generates the OCB entities preserving the names that we have previously defined when provisioning the devices, allowing us to replace sensors without affecting the entities.
- Register a new IoT station:** This service provides the registration of a new IoT station in the system. A brief description in code of the body of the request is shown below (see Figure 5). This operation is carried out by “Register IoT Entity” service (see table 4). The data model previously

defined by following the NGSI structure defined by FIWARE in OCB must be used. In addition, FIWARE-Service and FIWARE-ServicePath headers are used to identify greenhouse and station names in hierarchies.

Figure 5: Graphical representation of a JSON body to create an entity

- Current System Values and Historical Data:** This service allows users and applications to retrieve information in JSON format using REST API services. Table 4 shows the two endpoints required to use these services (*Historical Data* and *Historical Last Data*). These two services are essential for the platform since they are used in iVeg in the graphical part as well as in the use of GMaaS to know the system variables.
- GMaaS:** GMaaS provides useful models to be used. On the one hand, the climate model provides forecasts of internal greenhouse conditions up to next 72 hours, using current sensor data and external weather forecasts. On the other hand, the production model allows users to know crop production since the beginning of the season until the requested date. Finally, the irrigation model provides recommendations for irrigation needs in the next 72 hours. Detailed information about the development and use of GMaaS can be found in [44, 31].

The GMaaS service may be used in two ways. First, through a graphical interface where users can access via a web application to make requests and

view the results of weather, production and irrigation models. This option is particularly useful for farmers, as it allows them to make predictions on remarkable aspects such as the climate and irrigation of their greenhouses. The second option is through a REST API, which allows users, especially researchers, to invoke the models from any programming environment or software tool for simulation or prediction purposes.

- **iVeg:** iVeg is the end user application of the developed IoT platform. iVeg provides an online dashboard that enables users to access to consolidated data using the IoT approach. In Figure 6, a customizable panel is shown, allowing users to set up real-time and historical data visualization using graphics. Users can select the sensors from a drop-down list, and the system stores this configuration for next login. GMaaS is integrated as another feature of iVeg. iVeg manages requests to DSS models and show results in graphical and tabular formats. This functionality is specially useful for farmers, who can use model-based services to predict and estimate issues related to climate, production, and irrigation in their greenhouses for DSS purposes. When weather and irrigation models are requested, the system provides recommendations for control system inputs, such as target temperature, irrigation amount, irrigation duration, or irrigation nitrogen levels for the upcoming 72 hours. A data service is also available, so user can download resulting JSON data from the requests.

Figure 6: iVeg Dashboard

4.2. *Microalgae domain*

Another successful application of the architecture and methodology described in this article is an IoT platform dedicated to biomass production through microalgae cultivation (see Figure 3). This system is located at the Instituto de Investigación y Formación Agraria y Pesquera Andaluz (IFAPA) in La Cañada, Almería, Spain. With an area of approximately 5000 m², it contains facilities for microalgae cultivation, nutrient storage, and water supply services.

The plant includes two greenhouses: one with approximately 700 m² for tubular reactors (see Figure 3), ozonation systems and inoculum columns, and another with approximately 1200 m² for the Thinlayers and Raceways photobioreactors (see Figure 3). Additionally, two other larger Thinlayer and Raceways photobioreactors are located on an outdoor plot of 2100 m². In total, the plant has thirteen photobioreactors: three thin-layers, four raceways, three tubulars and three groups of three inoculum columns.

Photobioreactors are the space where the microalgae cultivation process takes place and allow the regulation of the parameters involved in microalgae growth. Precise control of pH, dissolved oxygen, and temperature is essential for microalgae cultivation, so sensors have been installed in each photobioreactor [50, 51].

Operators control the plant from a personal computer with SCADA software, which is an OPC UA client. This computer communicates with LabJack UE9 data acquisition boards installed in the plant via the Modbus TCP/IP protocol. Data is monitored in real time and subscribed to the OPC UA server through a FIWARE IoT Agent. Details about data integration and management processes are described in [52].

4.2.1. *Architecture*

During the second phase of the architecture development, new and improved functionalities were tested, providing an extension of the scenario previously described 4.1.2. In this new scenario, we can highlight the use of Cygnus to

store historical data and the customization of a new IoT agent that allows the integration of data between OPC UA and OCB (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Architecture and services in the microalgae sector

- IoT Agent OPC UA:** As outlined in the section 2.1.1 discussing OPC UA, this standard, developed by the OPC Foundation for industrial IoT, defines two primary entities: clients and servers. Communications between these entities is carried out using either request and response messages, or a publish and subscription model. Our architecture employs the OPC UA Agent as a client, enabling subscriptions to nodes formed by photobioreactor sensors. OPC UA represents an evolution of classic OPC, now supporting newer technologies like IoT. In our design, OPC UA serves as a data server, storing device-generated data. Each photobioreactor is connected to an OPC UA server, providing sensor data. The SCADA system acts as a client to the OPC UA server, providing information to users. This setup leads to a better sensor management, as each photobioreactor operates within an independent node. Additionally, the server offers a standardized data model for bidirectional communication, enabling control and data queries by external services.

Table 5: Entities used in the OCB for photobioreactors.

EntityId	EntityType	AttributesName	AttributesType	AttributesValue	MetadataName	MetadataType	MetadataValue
RW1	Photobioreactor	dissox,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.1.2024-03-04T21:00:00
RW2	Photobioreactor	dissox,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.2.2024-03-04T21:00:00
RW3	Photobioreactor	dissox,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.3.2024-03-04T21:00:00
RW4	Photobioreactor	dissox,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.4.2024-03-04T21:00:00
TL1	Photobioreactor	dissox,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.1.2024-03-04T21:00:00
TL2	Photobioreactor	dissox,...	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id.2.2024-03-04T21:00:00

The IoT agent serves as an intermediary translator between the OPC UA server and OCB, performing several tasks. Configuration involves setting up the agent with each OPC UA server node and specifying monitored variables, including active or lazy monitoring for attributes. Configuration parameters, such as OPC server, service, subservice IP addresses, as well as the agent communicating with OCB, are defined. The agent maintains a MongoDB database to store configurations, avoiding reconfiguration. Once configured, the agent automatically generates entities with attributes following the FIWARE OCB standard. This automation step avoids the need for manual OCB configuration. Adding new photobioreactors or sensors simply requires modifying the OPC UA agent, triggering automatic generation of entities and attributes. The use of these IoT agents offers advantages, allowing easy integration of smart sensors using different communication protocols like MQTT or LoRaWAN by generating new intermediate IoT agents.

- **OCB:** In our project, the entities are photobioreactors, weather stations and different kind of actuators, such as injection pumps, medium pumps, the irrigation head or wheel blades, among others. Table 5 shows the entities created in OCB. In addition, OCB also manages attributes of sensors and actuators, such as data type, their value and metadata. Entities and attributes are not generated from OCB. They are generated by the IoT Agent. Note that OCB does not store historical data, so the customization of the proposed architecture for this scenario uses Cygnus as another alternative to store data.

- **Cygnus:** As previously stated in section 2.1.2, Cygnus is dedicated to store historical data across various databases. In this scenario, Cygnus provides an endpoint for receiving notifications generated by OCB. Our approach involves Cygnus for storing data in both MongoDB and Postgres databases. Cygnus utilizes OCB subscription and notification features. A subscription is created in OCB by Cygnus, specifying the attributes for which notifications are needed upon updates to any entity properties.

4.2.2. Proposed services

This subsection shows the use of the new services developed to customize the IoT platform.

- **Provision IoT Devices:** In this case, new devices are connected to an OPC UA server (standard used in industrial sectors). First, OPC UA server is registered providing its IP address and the nodes we want to query. A feature of this GE is that it allows us to perform a complete automation of all the nodes of the OPC UA server, which facilitates the integration of a large number of sensors. In this case, Figure 8 shows graphically the body of the POST request with the necessary data to register two photobioreactor type devices (Raceway and Tubular) with their corresponding sensors. The IoT Agent will be in charge of creating the entities with the names established when registering the devices.

4.3. Agro-industrial domain

Finally, a third successful deployment of the architecture and methodology described in this article is a scenario of an agro-industrial district composed of two water sources (i.e., a solar desalination plant and the water utility network) and several consuming agents (i.e., three greenhouses and an office building). This small-scale agro-industrial district was chosen because it can be considered representative of an industrial-scale one.

Main objective of this scenario is to leverage IoT platform capabilities for optimizing the management of water networks in agro-industrial environments.

Figure 8: Graphical representation of a JSON body to create an IoT OPC UA Agent

Furthermore, a Model Predictive Control (MPC) strategy is introduced into the architecture. This approach is used to optimize the operational costs of water consumption taking into account parameters such as the supply costs of the desalination plant pump, and the costs associated with water consumption from the public water supply network, ensuring water needs are met. Components of the industrial district are described below:

- **Solar desalination plant:** The solar desalination plant used as a reference in the case study is based on the Solar Membrane Distillation (SMD) facility at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), Spain. A current image

of the plant is shown in figure 3. This installation was described in [53]. It consists of a solar field, which provides the thermal energy needed for the Membrane Distillation (MD) process, several MD modules and a heat exchanger that connects both systems. The plant is fully controlled and monitored, measuring the main variables of the distillation process such as pressure, temperature, and flow rate.

- **Greenhouses:** The greenhouses included in this scenario are based on the pilot greenhouse previously described. In this case, new entities will be in charge of recording the water needs of the greenhouses. In this proposal, greenhouses request water needs, which is supplied by the desalination plant.
- **Smart building:** The smart building in this scenario takes as reference the CIESOL building located on the campus of the University of Almería, Spain, 20 km from the PSA (see Figure 3). CIESOL building houses an extensive network of sensors for measuring indoor and outdoor environmental parameters such as solar radiation, temperature, humidity, wind speed, wind direction, precipitation and water consumption. It also has equipment for solar energy research, such as solar collectors, thermal storage systems, photovoltaic cells and measuring equipment. In this proposal, the building requests water needs, which is supplied by the desalination plant.

4.3.1. Architecture

During the final phase of the architecture development, new functionalities were tested, providing an extension of the previously described scenario. A MPC controller is included. It allows executing real-time operational strategies in the cloud. This feature is possible because of data model standardization and data integration. This contribution has been detailed in [54].

- **OCB:** In our proposal, a new functionality for these entities was introduced, which involves creating new attributes on the basis of the hydric

Figure 9: Architecture and services in the Agro-industrial sector

requirements of each sector. Table 6 displays the attributes of the variables produced by these entities according to the system's needs, while the external attributes column of the controller includes variables generated through the application of MPC control techniques. The purpose of integrating the external attributes of the controller within the entity is to enable these actuators to act as recipients of each sector's requirements, facilitating autonomous operations.

In our proposal, a new functionality for these entities has been introduced. It creates new attributes according to the water needs of each sector. The table 6 shows variable attributes produced by these entities according to system needs. In addition, new attributes generated by the MPC controller are added. The purpose of integrating external attributes of the controller in the entity is to allow these actuators to act as receivers of the requirements of each sector, making autonomous operations easier.

- **MPC Controller:** It deals with optimal water resource management. This service is located in Storage and processing layer (see Figure 9). It is controlled by a polling process and it allows querying the needs of each

Table 6: Entities used in the OCB for water requirements.

EntityId	EntityType	AttributesName	AttributesType	AttributesValue	MetadataName	MetadataType	MetadataValue
Solar desalination plant	Controller	$T_{cs,out}$, $T_{feed},...$	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id_1,2024-03-04T21:00:00
Water storage tank	Controller	L	Float	30.4	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id_2,2024-03-04T21:00:00
Greenhouse 1	Controller	$D_{GH1},...$	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id_3,2024-03-04T21:00:00
Greenhouse 2	Controller	$D_{GH2},...$	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id_4,2024-03-04T21:00:00
Greenhouse 3	Controller	$D_{GH3},...$	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id_1,2024-03-04T21:00:00
Smart building	Controller	$D_{OB},...$	Number, Float...	20, 40.5	String, timestamp...	Number, DateTime	id_2,2024-03-04T21:00:00

system through the REST service and inserting the new instructions into the column of external attributes controller of each entity (see Table 6). Details about the implementation of the MPC controller and its operation are described in [54].

- **Polling process:** This service is executed every 15 minutes. It retrieves data from the different industrial sectors through REST API requests and sending the new information to the MPC controller.

4.4. Additional scenarios

While this work is focused on real-world agroindustrial applications currently deployed using the proposed architecture, the platform has been designed with a modular and adaptable approach, allowing its application in various industries. So, the platform can be effectively used in other domains, like healthcare [55, 56] and logistics [57, 58]. In a healthcare context, it can be used in Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) [59] environments to enhance the safety and well-being of elderly individuals or those requiring assisted care. IoT-enabled devices such as motion sensors, smart wearables, and environmental monitors can collect data on user activity patterns that can be managed in our platform. In a logistics scenario, it can enhance supply chain efficiency and real-time asset tracking. IoT-enabled sensors, RFID tags, and GPS devices can collect data on vehicle locations, cargo conditions, and delivery schedules. By integrating this data into the platform, real-time monitoring of shipments may be enabled, allowing logistics operators to optimize delivery routes based on traffic conditions, weather forecasts, and warehouse availability.

5. Performance Evaluation and Scalability of the Platform

To evaluate the scalability of the platform, load tests were conducted in a controlled environment to analyze its behavior under different concurrency conditions. The infrastructure is deployed on a Kubernetes cluster using nodes with 2 vCPUs and 8 GB RAM, with horizontal auto-scaling enabled to dynamically manage increasing workloads. The system is designed to deploy additional instances when CPU usage exceeds 80%, ensuring that the platform maintains stable response times and high performance under heavy load conditions. During the tests, additional instances were automatically deployed at critical moments when the workload exceeded this threshold.

One of the primary bottlenecks identified in previous tests was the performance of MongoDB in concurrent write operations, due to the high frequency of incoming data from Orion Context Broker. To mitigate this issue, the system architecture was optimized by incorporating a MongoDB replica set, allowing write operations to be distributed across multiple database instances. This reduced CPU saturation and improved response times for real-time data storage operations, ensuring better scalability of the system.

The load tests were performed using Locust, a tool that simulates multiple concurrent users and measures system performance. Three key metrics were evaluated: Requests per Second (RPS), 95th Percentile Response Time (P95), and the Number of Active Instances in Kubernetes. During the experiments, the platform initially ran on a single instance and automatically deployed new replicas as the user load increased and CPU usage reached the 80% threshold. A temporary increase in latency was observed before the system autoscaled new instances, but response times stabilized once new replicas were provisioned automatically, demonstrating the system's ability to dynamically adapt to demand without compromising performance.

Additionally, MatLab Production Server (MPS) is fully compatible with Kubernetes, allowing the system to scale not only for data processing but also for executing computational models efficiently. By deploying MPS instances as

containerized services within the Kubernetes cluster, it is possible to dynamically allocate resources based on demand. This ensures that the execution of complex analytical models does not become a performance bottleneck, as additional MPS instances are automatically deployed when computational demand increases. The architecture allows horizontal scalability, where MPS instances are distributed across different nodes, optimizing the execution of MATLAB-based models in parallel and ensuring system responsiveness under high workloads.

Figure 10 illustrates the system's behavior during the load test. As the number of users increased, the system automatically scaled when CPU usage exceeded 80%, deploying new instances to maintain processing stability. Additionally, the MongoDB replica set effectively mitigated performance degradation in write operations by distributing the workload more efficiently and reducing node saturation.

The results confirm that the platform can horizontally scale to support an increase in users and processed data in the future. As part of continuous optimization, the integration of a load balancer with Nginx, the implementation of MongoDB sharding to better distribute write operations, and fine-tuning auto-scaling based on requests per second (RPS), in addition to CPU usage, are proposed to enable a more proactive response to traffic spikes.

the tests validate that the platform is highly scalable and efficient, ensuring stable performance even under heavy workloads. The combination of Kubernetes with horizontal auto-scaling, optimized storage using MongoDB replicas, and dynamic deployment of MPS instances allows the system to handle large volumes of traffic and concurrent processing without degradation in response times. These results confirm that the developed architecture is not only scalable but also has the capacity to support future growth without compromising stability.

Figure 10: Scalability evaluation of the platform

6. Results and Discussion

In this section, results obtained from deployed scenarios are presented. Contributions of our approach in comparison to the state-of-the-art in the field of heterogeneous data integration in IoT platforms are also discussed. Remarkable results were observed during the implementation and evaluation of the proposed system.

- **Use of standards:** By adopting standards, as the OMA NGSI data model, data heterogeneity and interoperability issues may be solved easier. Therefore, new modules may be developed to customize the platform according to specific needs. This encourages continuous improvement in development through developer communities.

- **Effective Integration of Heterogeneous Data:** Our approach successfully has integrated heterogeneous data from multiple sources into a unified IoT platform. Unlike other approaches that focus on simulation aspects, this proposal achieved data integration in real and heterogeneous industrial sectors, such as greenhouses, photobioreactors, desalination plants and smart buildings.
- **Use of Models as a Service:** GMaaS encapsulates a model as a cloud service. Integrating GMaaS into the proposed IoT platform provides a functionality to get support for forecasting and strategic decisions, improving crop cultivation process in the agricultural environment. Crop growth models, indoor weather models and irrigation requirements up to next 72 hours are used to get estimated predictions and plan farming operations effectively.
- **Scalability:** On the one hand, scenario components can be scaled out horizontally. New devices can be added to the Perception Layer. Related storage and processing services will be scaled consequently. The use of non-relational databases allows underlying databases to grow horizontally. Microservices allows scaling deployed services. On the other hand, new scenarios can also be added. The IoT platform will be scaled accordingly to include devices and services of the added scenarios.
- **Open Source Platform:** The choice of an open-source platform as the foundation of our system ensures transparency, collaboration, and continuous innovation.

Although our work has been developed from existing research in the field of data integration in IoT platforms, obtained results lead us to conclude that the described proposal offers several significant improvements using standard and open data models such as NSGI OMA, Models as a Service and platform scalability. As a result, the proposed approach for data management in industrial IoT environments has been successfully deployed in three industrial scenarios.

7. Conclusions and Future work

This work focuses on digital transformation on industrial domain narrowed to the development of IoT platforms. The IoT platform proposed in this work has been built using an architecture and a methodology oriented to provide features as interoperability, scalability and service-oriented. This platform covers the overall production cycle in various industrial scenarios. This includes sensor data acquisition, new device registration, data processing, data querying and multi-domain monitoring. Main features of the proposed IoT platform are a consequence of the proposed architecture and methodology as:

- **Use of a standard data model:** The platform uses a standardized data model based on entities, attributes, and metadata, derived from the OMA-NGSI data model of the FIWARE platform. This allows interoperability of devices and systems. Another FIWARE components, such as Orion Context Broker, Cygnus and IoTAgent are also used by the IoT platform.
- **Service-oriented architecture:** Platform data and processes are exposed as cloud services. On the one hand, current and historical data may be accessed through a REST API. This data service is used by both applications in the upper layer and directly by clients using REST API clients. On the other hand, data processing services and domain models may be also accessed through a REST API. The Greenhouse Model as a Service (GMaaS) component provides domain models (e.g. temperature, humidity, cultivation growth, and so on) as a cloud service. New domain specific models can be encapsulated in this component to be available as another cloud service.
- **Successful deployments:** The functionality of the IoT platform has been deployed using the described architecture and methodology in three working heterogeneous industrial scenarios (a set of greenhouses, a microalgae biorefinery and a small-scale agro-industrial environment). Each scenario has adapted to the reference architecture customizing network

protocols and devices and IoT devices at Perception layer, and storage systems and processing services at Data storage and processing layer. A successful integration has been achieved, so the platforms of these scenarios are interoperable.

Future work will focus on providing machine learning features to the platform for anomaly detection and process optimization. By leveraging predictive models trained on heterogeneous data sources, the system could proactively identify operational inefficiencies, detect potential failures in IoT devices, and optimize resource allocation across different industrial environments.

Additionally, exploring edge computing architectures will reduce cloud dependency by enabling real-time analytics closer to data sources. This would significantly improve response times and lower bandwidth consumption, making the platform more efficient for deployment in remote or environments with limited resources.

Finally, ensuring compliance with global IoT regulatory frameworks is essential for broader adoption. Future work will investigate how the platform can align with international standards such as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) for data privacy, ISO/IEC 30141 for IoT reference architecture, and cybersecurity frameworks like NIST IoT Cybersecurity Improvement Act. In addition, challenges such as mitigating denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks, securing firmware updates, and managing identity spoofing remain critical aspects requiring ongoing research and adaptation of security best practices.

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